

Literary Celebrity and Political Activism: Wole Soyinka's Nobel Prize Lecture and the Anti-Apartheid Struggle

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Abstract

In 1986 the Nigerian writer, Wole Soyinka, was awarded the Nobel Prize for literature. This paper considers the role of the Nobel Prize in the construction, promotion and cementing of literary celebrity, addressing the ways in which the prize augments Soyinka's literary and political renown, already substantial at the time of the award. It takes as focus Soyinka's Nobel lecture and his decision to leverage the global platform afforded him to highlight the struggle against apartheid. The lecture is structured around a refusal to concede the exceptionalism of the South African state, and around a framing of apartheid as a pan-African catastrophe. In the Nobel lecture, Soyinka levels a comprehensive accusation against European racism which he conceives as directly implicated in the ideological underpinning of apartheid policies. Dedicating the address to Mandela and taking his life as paradigm, Soyinka uses his own presence in Stockholm as a subversive supplement to Mandela's absence and addresses the crimes of apartheid both within their particular temporal and geographical context and as a means to expose the global scourge of racism.

Keywords: Wole Soyinka; Nobel Prize; Nelson Mandela; apartheid; literary celebrity; celebrity activism.

Introduction

This paper considers the celebrity activism of Wole Soyinka, the Nigerian playwright, poet, autobiographer, essayist, human rights activist, political prisoner and Africa's first and only black laureate of the Nobel Prize for literature. It takes as focus Soyinka's decision to dedicate the Nobel Prize lecture to Nelson Mandela, and to place the global celebrity garnered by the awarding of the prize in dialogue with Mandela's renown and with the anti-apartheid struggle that he had come to embody. Soyinka's decision to capitalize deliberately on the authority now conferred upon him and to devote the lecture almost entirely to an analysis of the depravities of

apartheid does not divert attention from continental Africa: rather, within his censure of apartheid South Africa he enfold a far-reaching critique of European racism that invalidates the exonerating construal of South Africa's exceptionalism. Apartheid is framed as an instance and extension of European constructions of race and as an affront to the continent as a whole. The global stage afforded Soyinka is deliberately and subversively exploited to undermine the cultural assumptions that underlie the prize and to call to account an audience he perceives as profoundly implicated in the ideological underpinnings of both the apartheid regime and of European colonialism in Africa.

This paper reads Soyinka's Nobel Prize address in the context of literary celebrity studies. While analyses of literary celebrity have tended to focus on issues of personal cachet, visibility, authenticity, promotion and self-promotion and on the economics of fame, less attention has been paid to the association between literary celebrity and political activism.¹ Arthur Rose's study of Samuel Beckett, Jorge Luis Borges and J.M. Coetzee, *Literary Cynics*, notes the leveraging of authorial fame in order to give prominence to the political commitments of the writer: in the case of the Nobel laureates, Beckett and Coetzee, their global status, enhanced by the prize, is used to publicize political causes espoused by the authors (2017, 21).² Lorraine York's analysis in *Literary Celebrity in Canada* provides a useful point of departure. Predicating her discussion of literary celebrity as a struggle for cultural authority on the theories of P. David Marshall in *Celebrity and Power: Fame in Contemporary Culture* and of Pierre Bourdieu in *The Field of Cultural Production: Essays on Art and Literature*, York determines: "those who are given special, elevated status as literary celebrities are given extra latitude to speak and to be listened to" (2007, 15). She draws attention to the capacity of literary celebrity to empower and

¹ Of works that consider literary celebrity the most notable are Joe Moran's *Star Authors: Literary Celebrity in America* and Loren Glass's *Authors Inc.: Literary Celebrity in the Modern United States, 1880-1980*. Two reviews, Anders Ohlsson, Torbjörn Forslid and Ann Steiner's "Literary Celebrity Reconsidered" and Rebecca Braun and Emily Spiers' "Introduction: Re-viewing Literary Celebrity", trace the development of theories of literary celebrity. While all these works consider the social effects of literary celebrity and the association between literary celebrity and cultural authority, the relationship between literary celebrity and political activism does not receive extensive attention.

² Worth noting is that Rose argues for an underlying ambivalence or cynicism latent in the declared political positions of the authors he discusses: thus the writers maintain "both a commitment to their projects, and a 'zealous disbelief' about them" (2017, 22). The same claim cannot be made for Soyinka who maintains an unswerving and unambiguous conviction of the validity of the political positions he espouses. In Soyinka's case, as is argued below, cynicism is directed at the premises underlying the prize itself.

validate authorial intervention and to the ways in which it is bound to a public responsiveness to the writer that derives from the sense that he or she is uniquely equipped to articulate urgent public concerns. The broader perspective she invites allows for a new examination of the associations between literary celebrity and political commitment. This accords with Soyinka's understanding of the pressing political responsibilities of the writer and with his determination to place his own renown in the service of his convictions.

The consideration of the ways in which political engagement intersects with literary celebrity allows for an examination of both the content of Soyinka's Nobel Prize address and the extraordinary circumstances of its delivery. Soyinka's scathing indictment of the apartheid state whose policies, he argues, are spawned in Europe, is both lecture and performance: alert to the burden of precedence and to the global resonance of the presence of a black African writer in Stockholm, Soyinka shapes the address to radically contest the blatant Eurocentrism of the cultural assumptions that underlie the prize, and to re-position Africa, and South Africa in particular, as the pivot of world attention.

Writer and Righter

In a 2009 address to the International Human Rights Commission entitled "Writer and Righter," another Nobel Prize winner, the Irish poet Seamus Heaney, relates extensively to the ethical responsibilities of the artist, questioning whether his obligations coincide with those of the "righter," the human rights activist committed to political action in contexts of conflict, oppression and repression: "Whether, to put it another way, ethical obligation shadows the aesthetic vocation" (2010, 9). The dilemma Heaney voices here has no place in Soyinka's *oeuvre*: he has repeatedly made explicit his sense of the spuriousness of the distinction between the aesthetic and the political, upholding a poetics that is generated by the imperative of political solidarity.

From the earliest stages of Soyinka's career, the perception of the intermeshing of the two aspects of his public persona—writer and activist—has had extraordinary tenacity. Biodun Jeyifo who equates Soyinka's stature with that of public intellectuals like Ngugi wa Thiong'o, Mongo Beti and Nawal el Saadawi, draws attention to a celebrity that stems as much from the visibility and audibility of the political positions he has adopted as from his literary output:

"Unquestionably, the most widely discussed aspect of Soyinka's public personality is that of his

fame as one of Nigeria's most uncompromising and vigorous human rights campaigners, and perhaps the fiercest and most consistent opponent of the African continent's slew of dictators and tyrants" (2003, 7). The widespread perception of Soyinka's ethical stature, his characterization as "the abrasive conscience for the nation of Nigeria and for the African continent" (Jaggi 1994, 56), is corroborated by his history of political militancy and by his persecution by the regimes he opposed: in 1965 he was accused of occupying the Western Nigerian Broadcasting service in an act of protest against the Western Nigerian general elections, an offense for which he was later acquitted on a technicality. In 1967, during the Nigerian civil war, Soyinka was imprisoned by the government of General Yakubu Gowon and was kept in isolation for two years. His experience in prison forms the basis of his memoir *The Man Died: Prison Notes of Wole Soyinka*, the title derived from Soyinka's assertion, "[t]he man dies in all who keep silent in the face of tyranny" (1972, 13). Soyinka's vociferous opposition to the government of General Sani Abacha between 1993 and 1998 resulted in his exile and the pronouncement of a death sentence *in absentia*. Soyinka has continued to voice an unsparing non-partisan critique of brutality and corruption wherever it is manifest, both in Africa and across the globe, often at high personal cost. Any discussion of Soyinka's celebrity must necessarily take into account the congruity of his literary stature and of his political integrity in the public eye.

South Africa in the writings of Wole Soyinka

Despite the broad ambit of Soyinka's censure of violations of human rights across Africa, his engagement with South Africa and with the crisis of apartheid assumes particular intensity. The extent of Soyinka's attentiveness to the apartheid state has been noted by Leon de Kock (1987) and David Attwell (2003) who point to the ways in which apartheid figures as a crux in his political thinking and in his writing, and as one of the motivating forces of his politics of resistance. In a particularly dense and complex argument, Attwell traces a shift in Soyinka's South African writing away from what he terms a "mythopoeic cultural nationalism" (2003, 33) towards an increasing cosmopolitanism and a recourse to discourses of universal human rights characteristic of modernity, that culminate in the Nobel Prize lecture. His discussion of the lecture directs attention to Soyinka's ameliorative evocation of a future time in which Europe detaches itself from the monstrosity of apartheid and affirms the promise of a community of nations bound by notions of equality, a universalism in which, as Attwell wryly notes, "Europe is

scarcely able to recognize itself” (2003, 41). The examination in this paper of the place of South Africa in the Nobel lecture emphasizes Soyinka’s lengthy analysis of the present moment in which apartheid is still intact, still sustained, in his resonant metaphor, by the umbilical cord that binds it to its European progenitors (1987, 767).

In his autobiography (2007) which follows *Ake*, the exploration of his childhood, Soyinka records the formative effect of his early encounters with the effects of apartheid and their role in driving his extensive involvement in the protests directed by the British Anti-Apartheid Movement, particularly in the disinvestment campaign. He relates to the contaminant of apartheid as both a keenly felt personal injury and as an offense directed against the African continent:

South Africa, however, occupied a special place of bafflement, rage and despair. Awareness of that degraded zone of existence on the soil of our own continent, the apprehension of a world that assigned to one’s race a condition of subhumanity, was all-consuming. We began to prepare ourselves for the day when we would reclaim that humanity—by force of arms if needed. (2007, 34)

For Soyinka, apartheid constantly spills over geographic borders. In the passage that directly follows this analysis, he relates to his own experience of British racism: “This obsession with the humiliation of racist entrenchment in southern Africa was not one of bloodless empathy—we did after all savour mild doses of that condition in our encounters with the white natives on their own territory” (2007, 34). The savagely ironic deflection of a racialized lexicon back to the colonialist centre and the casting of European racism within the compass of South African apartheid is typical of Soyinka’s method.

The running sore of the apartheid state is a theme Soyinka returns to repeatedly in both his drama and in his poetry. His first play, *The Invention*, staged at London’s Royal Court Theatre in 1959, is a satire in which he imagines a world destabilized by an explosion in which all racial characteristics are expunged. South African scientists finding themselves in a suddenly deracialized world must scramble to invent an antidote that will reconstitute evidence of identity in order to salvage a world order predicated on an obsessive pathology of racial stratification. The play becomes the occasion for a wider consideration of a history of global racism, exemplified by the international flavour of the racial epithets the scientists evoke: “At a press of the button, [his invention] will distinguish between the Wog, the Nigger, the Dago, the Jew, the

half-breed, the half-caste, the semi-breed, the inter-breed and their several components, and any other permutation and combination of the aforementioned races, right back to the sixth or seventh root of the individual's genealogy" (2005, 29). The scientists' progress is anxiously monitored by British and American envoys whose vested interest in the restoration of racial division is clear. Despite the weakness of the play and the heavy-handedness of its satire, it is, as Charles Larson suggests, remarkable for the blatancy of the association it makes between the racial underpinning of South Africa's policies and those of Western liberal democracies (1971, 81).

Soyinka's absorption with the matter of South Africa is evident in his epic poem *Ogun Abibiman*. Published in the aftermath of 1976, the poem is dedicated to "the dead and maimed of the Soweto uprising" and includes a lament for the victims of Sharpeville and a warning of the dormant retaliatory violence attendant on apartheid brutality:

Sharpeville
Bared its teeth, and *that*
Proved no sleeping dog
Though the kind world let it lie. (1980, 6)

The poem was occasioned by the 1976 declaration of war on the regime in Rhodesia by Samora Machel, the president of Mozambique, an event Soyinka envisioned as heralding the impending end of apartheid through armed resistance. Soyinka's certainty in the inevitability of historical process was thwarted by the signing of the Nkomati accord in 1984, a non-aggression pact between Mozambique and South Africa, which he considered a shameful betrayal of African solidarity and which he decries both in the Nobel Prize lecture and in the poem "Apologia (Nkomati)" in the volume, *Mandela's Earth and Other Poems*. *Ogun Abibiman* draws together the figure of Ogun, the Yoruba deity, and the figure of Shaka, the warrior-king of the amaZulu and potent symbol across Africa of resistance to, and victory over, the European presence in Africa. Shaka, celebrated by Soyinka as "Africa's most renowned nation builder" (1980, 23), figures as the epic hero of both Léopold Senghor's *Chaka* (1951) and Mazisi Kunene's *Emperor Shaka the Great: A Zulu Epic* (1979). de Kock has pointed to the directness of *Ogun Abibiman*'s relevance to a South Africa audience that derives only partly from the evocation of the figure of Shaka: "Nowhere other than in the poem *Ogun Abibiman* does Soyinka's work so directly

challenge the moral resolve of his South African reader than in this factual narrative which doubles as a metaphorical indictment of all who tolerate political cruelty, even if only by the complicity of silence” (1987, 134).

The prominence of South Africa as the object of Soyinka’s activism is evident in both the Nobel lecture and in his post-Nobel volume of poems, *Mandela’s Earth and Other Poems*, discussed below. In both instances, Soyinka turns to the figure of Mandela, using Mandela’s symbolic authority to express the full weight of his censure of apartheid

The Nobel Prize for Literature: the making of celebrity

Soyinka’s concern with the depredations of the apartheid regime culminates in the Nobel Prize lecture. Since the focus of this paper is the use to which Soyinka puts the platform granted him by the award, I address the role of the Nobel Prize in the construction and augmentation of literary celebrity. The significance of the Nobel Prize in determining literary value and its role in the promotion and amplification of the renown of the writer has been widely considered. Richard Jewell’s examination of the history of the prize suggests that the award is not simply a recognition of merit but is actively implicated in the generation of canonicity (2000). In Rebecca Braun’s account of the fetishization of the Nobel Prize, she considers the prize’s effect as fundamentally transformative: the literary renown enjoyed by the author prior to its award is reconstructed as literary celebrity, its reach and impact now exponentially increased: “what makes the Nobel Prize, as an awarding body and cultural event in one, different to its many other lower profile counterparts seeking to curate literatures is the explicit manner in which it facilitates the simultaneous production and consumption of celebrity within the literary field” (2011, 321).

Perhaps the most astute analysis of the impact of literary prizes on the manufacture of celebrity and of most relevance to a consideration of Soyinka, is Graeme Huggan’s *The Post-Colonial Exotic*. Huggan sites the literary prize industry in a post-colonial context, paying particular attention to its ramifications in Africa. While he focuses primarily on the Booker prize, his insights have relevance for an understanding of the cultural economy of the Nobel. Like Braun and York, Huggan draws heavily on Bourdieu’s exemplary analysis of literary culture in *The Field of Cultural Production: Essays on Art and Literature*, adopting his notion of the “consecrated” text. Bourdieu’s definition of the field of cultural production as “the site of

struggles in which what is at stake is the power to impose the dominant definition of the writer and therefore to delimit the population of those entitled to take part in the struggle to define the writer” (1993, 42) is integrated into Huggan’s examination of the occluded ideologies at work behind prizes like the Booker or the Nobel. Like the Booker, the Nobel possesses and exercises “a politics of literary recognition” particularly operative in the case of Soyinka (Huggan 2001, 118).

The awarding of the Nobel Prize to Soyinka in 1986 was perceived world-wide as an event of radical significance. The fame that attaches to the Nobel was magnified by the precedent—Soyinka was the first black African to be awarded the prize for literature. The prize has since been awarded to the white South African writers, Nadine Gordimer and J.M. Coetzee. It has been presented for literary excellence in 25 languages, 18 of which are European languages. It has never been granted for literature in an African language. The frequently leveled criticism that the prize is the prerogative of white European men is one borne out by the statistics. Of the 114 Nobel Prizes for literature only 14 have been awarded to women. Toni Morrison is the only black woman to have been awarded the prize.

The Eurocentrism of the prize is undeniable: as late as 1977, Artur Lundkvist, a member of the academy, defended its exclusivity in terms that expose his, and by implication, the Academy’s, positioning of Europe as a geographical center and Africa and Asia as both spatially and culturally peripheral—a stance undisguised by the minor apologetics of the quotation marks around “remote”: “The academy is often reproached for thus neglecting the literatures of Asia and Africa and other ‘remote’ parts. But I doubt if there is so far very much to find there. It is a question of literatures that have not achieved that level of development ... that can make them truly significant” (Espmark 1991, 141, quoted in Jewell 2000, 106). The Eurocentric bias in fact shifts very little with the award to Soyinka. In the tribute to Soyinka at the Nobel dinner, his literary identity is carefully assigned and his prowess is validated by his capacity to assimilate a European corpus into an exoticized African orature: “Dear Mr. Soyinka, in your versatile writings you have been able to synthesize a very rich heritage from your own country, ancient myths and old traditions, with literary legacies and traditions of European culture” (Award ceremony speech).

In the case of the award to Soyinka, the status of the Nobel as the ultimate purveyor of celebrity status and the image of the laureate as grateful recipient of the material and cultural rewards of the prize is perhaps more conflictual. The members of the Academy were well aware of the criticism levelled at the prize: the award to a black African writer was in part an attempt to restore the failing reputation of the prize and to paper over the cracks in the façade of cultural infallibility that had begun to appear in the Swedish Academy's carefully cultivated image of impartiality based on undisclosed criteria of literary excellence. The assumption by the members of the Academy of the role of a lofty pantheon, of literary gatekeepers, impervious to the stain of political realities, and the lack of transparency about their qualifications to arbitrate on questions of the value of world literature, were increasingly under attack. Unusually then, Soyinka's prize carries elements of symbiosis: he was indeed thrust into the global spotlight to become the beneficiary of the celebrity-making apparatus of the prize. At the same time, the renown, and indeed legitimacy of the prize, was shored up by Soyinka's literary fame and by his political credentials, validated by his long association with human rights activism—all of which were in place before the prize was awarded.

The Reception of the Nobel Prize

The prize had been eagerly anticipated in Nigeria and across the continent. When it was finally awarded in 1986, it was celebrated across Africa, and in Nigeria, Soyinka was hailed as a national hero. In an interview with Anthony Appiah in the aftermath of the award, Soyinka signals his understanding of the broader, transnational significance of the prize:

[I]t's of great importance, I think, not so much to me as to the literary craftsmen of my continent, to those who share my political concerns for the continent, to those who share the longing for a brotherhood/sisterhood which transcends the African continent and reaches out into the diaspora. The way in which the Prize has been received by people all over the world, particularly the African diaspora—in the West Indies, in the United States, and across the various language boundaries—has reinforced my insistent conviction that the African world is not limited by the African continent. (1988, 777)

Soyinka's sense of the prize as a groundbreaking acknowledgment of black achievement and as affirming black solidarity is verified by the reception of the prize across the world. In a two-part special edition of *Black America Literature Forum*, dedicated entirely to Soyinka, the leading black American literary critic and intellectual, Henry Louis Gates Jr. records humorously and poignantly his jubilation at the award. The sense of a global black stake in the prize and of long-

delayed vindication is palpable in his assertion: “[H]is victory was our victory: Black, Pan-African, African, African-American, Nigerian, Yoruba. It was the victory of an old friend, but it was a victory for our literature, and for its criticism” (1988, 423).

Bernth Lindfors, a prominent scholar of Nigerian literature and the founding editor of the influential journal, *Research in African Literatures*, has traced the complexity of Nigerian responses to the prize: the prevalent reaction to the award among African intellectuals was one of triumph tempered by scorn at the prize’s blatant Eurocentrism. The ambivalence towards the Nobel is best embodied by Chinua Achebe’s acerbic observation: “One of us has proved that we can beat the white man at his own game” (quoted in Lindfors, 1988, 487).³ Amongst certain Nigerian intellectuals the reaction was however, wholly negative: the long simmering feud or *bolekaja* (literally “come let’s fight”)⁴ between Soyinka and Chinweizu, one of Nigeria’s most prominent public intellectuals, was played out in the public sphere. Chinweizu’s opposition to the Nobel Prize was rooted in an extended history of mutual enmity: Chinweizu, Onwuchewka Jemie and Ihechukwu Madubuike’s article, “Towards the Decolonization of African Literature”,⁵ published originally in the journal *Okike* in 1975 and reprinted in *Transition* in the same year, lambasted Soyinka for his obscurantist poetics and for his reliance on a European canon. Soyinka published his response in the same issue: “Neo-Tarzanism: The Poetics of Pseudo-Tradition” disparagingly indicts what he considered the crude Negritude politics of “the troika” (1975, 38). The conflict reached particularly vituperative heights in the Nigerian *Guardian* from 1985 around the question of the Nobel Prize, reflecting a widespread sense of its imminence. In his 1985 article “The Nobel Prize Brouhaha” prior to the award, and in the 1989 article “Cries for Freedom,” Chinweizu frames the prize as a material signifier of Western culture and its pursuit as a shameful vestige of subaltern identification with colonial power. In “Cries for Freedom” Chinweizu pointedly avoids mentioning Soyinka by name, a tactic that does little to disguise the degree of animosity: “in 1986, the Royal Swedish Academy made an ass of itself in African eyes by conferring the Nobel Prize for Literature on an extremely Euroassimilationist brand of writing which most Africans don’t bother to read, and which many see as tainted with quisling qualities.

³ The observation forms the title of Lindfors’ 1988 article on the Nigerian reception of the prize

⁴ The meaning of the term is considered both by Bernth Lindfors (1988) and by James Gibbs (1988) in their analyses of Soyinka’s Nobel Prize

⁵ The article was later expanded into their seminal work, *Towards the Decolonization of African Literature* (1983), which condemns all manifestations of “Euroassimilation.”

... Some say the 1986 award was a triumph display, advertising a continuing attempt to mould African culture in Europe's image" (1989, 13).

The public acrimony and the conflicting claims to cultural legitimacy served to heighten Soyinka's public visibility and renown rather than to detract from it. Nevertheless, his determination to use the Nobel lecture to launch an extended attack on the tenets of Eurocentrism so scathingly condemned by Chinweizu, and to position South Africa as a fundamentally African cause, as an attestation of pan-African interdependence and as the dominant instance of European structural racism, is in part a response to and a refutation of the criticism levelled at him.

"This Past Must Address Its Present": Soyinka's Nobel Prize Lecture

Soyinka's decision to relate extensively to the plight of South Africa in his Nobel Prize address must be placed within the context of events in the 1980s. Widespread civil unrest in South Africa and the declaration of a partial state of emergency with the granting of extreme powers to the state in South Africa in 1985 placed the brutality of the Nationalist government under international scrutiny. In the civil unrest that followed the declaration of emergency, 28 people were killed and thousands detained. In 1986, the tenth anniversary of the Soweto Uprising, the South African government reinstated a state of emergency, putting draconian measures into place to forestall all commemorative events. The Anti-Apartheid Movement, based in Britain and dedicated to the mobilization of opposition to apartheid rule, stepped up measures to encourage disinvestment in South Africa. In 1986 the Republican House of Representatives overrode the veto exercised by Ronald Regan and passed the Comprehensive Anti-Apartheid Act which banned all new U.S. investment in South Africa, specifying the prohibition of sales to the police and military. At the same time, the ANC focused the anti-apartheid campaigns on the figure of Nelson Mandela (Klein 2009, 466-69). The 1978 celebration of Mandela's 60th birthday signalled this new emphasis, although it was only in the 1980s that the campaign took root as a focal point of international anti-apartheid activity.

Despite the heightened public visibility of the depredations of apartheid and of Mandela as figurehead of the struggle, Soyinka's decision to focus on Mandela and on South Africa was not self-evident. In the interview referred to above, Appiah questions this decision. Soyinka's

response elucidates his understanding of the enormous potential coverage of the event and the opportunity afforded him to leverage the global attention now trained upon him:

Appiah: I noticed that when you gave your Nobel lecture, you chose to discuss apartheid and southern Africa. Did you feel that that was a particularly important thing to do at that moment?

Soyinka: A lot of my writing has been concerned with injustice, with inhumanity, with racism, inside and outside of my immediate environment, which is Nigeria. This is a world platform, and I could not think of any more appropriate moment for voicing this particular level of my literary concerns. I thought it was most appropriate, yes. (1988, 777-778)

Soyinka's Nobel Prize address is dedicated to Nelson Mandela. Inexplicably omitted from the transcript of the speech on the Nobel Prize internet site, the dedication can be heard sonorously uttered on the recording. By invoking his name at the start, Soyinka uses his own presence on the stage in Stockholm to signal and stand in for Mandela's tangible absence, talking for him as much as of him. Mandela is made viscerally present partly because Soyinka's own biography recalls elements of Mandela's life: a shared history of dissidence, armed struggle, imprisonment and isolation in the service of the defence of human rights. The lecture, delivered on perhaps the most global of all stages, is in the first instance an act of restitution, aimed at contesting the effacement of Mandela's presence and the silencing of his voice under apartheid rule. The act of nomination inaugurates an underlying thematic of exposure, both of the specific depravity of the apartheid state and of the entrenchment of European racism that Soyinka pursues throughout the address.

From the 1950 Suppression of Communism Act, through numerous reiterations and revisions, South African law prohibited the publication of the words of any person in South Africa banned under its laws. Photographs of the banned could not be distributed so that no vestige of the bodily presence of the outlawed might trigger identification and insurrection. Mandela, "the man with no face" (Tomaselli and Shepperson 2009, 26) surfaces only rarely and fleetingly during his 27-year incarceration in authorized photographs intended to place the South African authorities in a positive light. In this forced disappearance, the banned or incarcerated subject assumes the status of the quasi-dead. Evoking Mandela's haunting absence, Elleke Boehmer states: "To his dear ones as to the nation at large, Prisoner 466/64, the inmate of Cell No. 5, became in effect, a bodiless, intangible presence: a spectre, a ghost" (2008, 149).

In Simon Gikandi's examination of Mandela's expunged presence in South African literature, he draws attention to an unmentionability that paradoxically heightens Mandela's spectral omnipresence. Gikandi suggests that the tangibility of the figure of Mandela is powerful enough to rescind his enforced anonymity: the fact that "he is there because he is not there" undergirds what Gikandi identifies as "a poetics of indirection, entering the public sphere through a language that says one thing and means another" (2016,14). Thus, in a transgressive undoing of this imposed, defensive indirection, Soyinka delivers the Nobel Prize lecture under the sign of Mandela, its content subordinated to Mandela's authority, here conceived as formidably present.

More than half of the address is dedicated to an analysis of the history of the genesis and development of apartheid and the implementation of its policies. Yet it does not open with an immediate reference to South Africa, nor, as was to be expected, with some reference to Nigeria. Despite Soyinka's own sense of the award as a national achievement, Nigeria figures only tangentially in the lecture. Instead, it opens with a geographical displacement to Kenya and to the Mau Mau uprising (1952-1960). In 1959, during the uprising against British colonial rule in Kenya, 11 political prisoners held at the Hola camp were battered to death by British soldiers. Despite initial attempts to cover up the atrocity and to claim that the prisoners had died after drinking poisoned water, the incident was raised in the British Parliament and an enquiry into the events was established. The atrocities at the Hola camp formed the basis of a theatrical improvisation performed at the Royal Court Theatre in 1959 where Soyinka was a dramaturgist and in which he was to have participated as actor. In the anecdote that opens the lecture, Soyinka recounts his refusal to come onto the stage to participate in the dramatic representation of the atrocity. Using this instance of an aberrant and distressing failure to validate his own craft, he questions the legitimacy of an artistic response to historical reality: "What then was the problem? It was one, I believe, that affects most writers. When is playacting rebuked by reality? When is fictionalizing presumptuous? What happens after playacting?" (1987, 763).

This opening anecdote carries a dual significance: the incident that Soyinka recounts is more than a plea for an art that is relevant only when it is made answerable to political extremity. It is not simply a reprisal or anticipation of the responses of other Nobel laureates like those of Seamus Heaney or Nadine Gordimer whose answers to these questions rehearse Czesław Miłosz's renowned interrogation of his own poetics: "What is poetry which does not

save / Nations or people? / A connivance with official lies” (1988 “Dedication”). Rather in emphasizing an instance where the writer is silenced by the impact of reality, and where that artistic paralysis is framed as a crucial and ethical response, he relocates the meaning of his presence on the stage in Stockholm, defining himself primarily as dissident and activist and subordinating his cultural and literary pre-eminence to protest. In this subversive framing of the moment, the value of a prize for literature is called into question. The overt politicization of the address and its accusatory nature, the implied association between the culpability of the British audience of the theatrical improvisation in the events enacted on stage in 1959 and the implication of a European audience in Stockholm in 1986 in the historical patterns he traces in the lecture is made uncomfortably clear. In Soyinka’s performance, the liberal humanist belief in the ameliorative properties of literature is made to seem impotent. He thus deliberately transgresses a historical prescription of the Nobel Prize lecture as it is elucidated by Rebecca Braun: “laureate writers apparently inevitably subscribe to the same inherently fetishised, high-minded ideal of literature as underlies Nobel’s resiliently opaque will. Literature is presented to Nobel audiences down through the ages as an intellectually and morally elevating cause, which is naturally fronted by the author” (2011, 127).

The placing of the Hola camp incident at the opening of the address is significant equally because of the lines Soyinka draws between this incident and his analysis of apartheid South Africa: in his construction of racial suffering in Africa, the contemplation of the Hola camp massacre segues into a consideration of Sharpeville and a tracing of the historical trajectories of apartheid violence: “They, white supremacist breed, have indeed come a long way in their definition of their chosen enemy since Hola Camp. They have come an incredibly long way since Sharpeville when they shot unarmed, fleeing Africans in the back” (1987, 764). In the bitterly ironic progression that Soyinka follows, advance is measured by the methods by which Africans are killed—the African beaten to death or shot in the back because he is indistinguishable from an animal slowly becomes an adversary whose humanity is validated only by the increasingly sophisticated weaponry needed to dispose of him. The shaming revival of the Hola camp massacre and its placement with South Africa on a continuum of atrocity thus underlies the accusation that Soyinka levels at a global audience: South Africa’s perverse history is exposed as an appendix to a European colonialism vindicated by a metaphysics grounded in racist assumptions: Soyinka’s evocation of Hegel, Locke, Hume and Voltaire, “the unabashed theorists

of racial superiority and denigrators of the African history and being,” exposes both the hollowness of claims to cultural superiority and the implication of western philosophy in a politics of violence (1987, 766).⁶

A similar emphasis is to be found in Soyinka’s volume *Mandela’s Earth and Other Poems*, published in 1988 in what Tanure Ojaide terms “the copious afterglow of the Nobel award” (2015, 92). Soyinka’s status as a Nobel laureate meant that wide critical and public attention were trained on the volume. While critics single out poems like “Muhammad Ali at the Ringside. 1985” and “Cremation of a Wormy Caryatid” for praise, it is the South African poems that command most scrutiny. The poems in the volume’s first section, “Mandela’s Earth,” which take the apartheid regime as subject, often draw directly on the Nobel Prize lecture and translate its concerns into poetic form. The section includes the poem, “Like Rudolph Hess, The Man Said!” to which Soyinka refers in the lecture and which addresses the South African government’s comparison of Mandela to Rudolph Hess. Despite the increasingly phantasmagoric nature of the poem’s satire in which Mengele is transfigured into Mandela in a series of linguistic and thematic pyrotechnics, its premise is clear: the temerity of the equation of Mandela with Rudolph Hess by a racist government whose policies draw on Nazi ideologies of racial purity promulgated in Europe, prompts the poem’s unchecked fury.

Take a Good Look

If, for Soyinka, apartheid is the culmination of European constructions of race which perpetuate the injustice that Europe has perpetrated with respect to the continent as a whole, then the global stage afforded him in the Nobel address provides a richly subversive occasion for riposte. At the heart of the Nobel Prize lecture Soyinka stages a performance of his own embodied blackness in the face of a pervasive repudiation of his humanity on the part of his Western interlocutors: dressed in the *agbada*, the sartorial marking of his national identity, Soyinka demands that his audience train their gaze on him. Addressed ostensibly to the architects and perpetrators of apartheid policy, this injunction is simultaneously directed at the European audience he confronts:

⁶ In the Nobel Prize lecture Soyinka includes Montesquieu in his designation of philosophers whose work is tainted by their racism. In *You Must Set Forth at Dawn*, he apologizes profusely for this oversight (2007, 21). When the lecture was published in PMLA in 1987, the reference to Montesquieu was omitted.

Dare we skirt the edge of hubris and say to them: Take a good look. Provide your response. In your anxiety to prove that this moment is not possible, you had killed, maimed, silenced, tortured, exiled, debased and dehumanized hundreds of thousands encased in this very skin, crowned with such hair, proudly content with their very being? How many potential partners in the science of heart transplant have you wasted? How do we know how many black South African scientists and writers would have stood here, by now, if you had had the vision to educate the rest of the world in the value of a great multi-racial society? (1987, 766)

In the subversive instruction, “take a good look” and his direction of the audience’s scrutiny to the features, “this very skin, crowned with such hair” that have formed the basis of racial classification, Soyinka evokes both Ralph Ellison and Frantz Fanon’s construction of the white gaze. Ellison’s exposure of the invisibility of the black subject, his reduction to a phantom since only whiteness can lay claim to presence, is repudiated by Soyinka’s disruptive claim to being. At the same time, the demand to take a good look reprises the child’s cry, “Look, a Negro!” in Fanon’s *Black Skin, White Masks* that exposes the black body as a locus of fear and loathing (2008, 84). The child’s designation of difference is transformed by its voicing by the black subject—here made an agent, commanding the gaze rather than its despised object. Despite the setting, Soyinka’s claim to visibility is not a function of authorial presence. Rather an authority of presence derives from Soyinka’s construction of himself as understudy: in the inconceivable moment of the award of a Nobel to a Black African, he re-replaces Mandela on an international stage and stands in for the unrealized presence of anonymous South Africans and Africans deprived of this possibility. The gaze that Soyinka invites from his audience is implicitly countered by a black gaze directed outward. In this remarkable historical instance, he addresses a white audience now made foreign: “on this occasion I do not need to address *us*. We know, and we embrace our mission. It is the *other* that this precedent seizes the opportunity to address” (1987, 765).

This ironic turning of the tables, the construction of Europe as the other and the re-casting of Africa as the inclusive collective, exposes Soyinka’s attitude to the mantle of celebrity he now wears: neither grateful nor gracious, he signals his awareness of the tokenism at its heart. His address is a jeremiad delivered in the bastion of European cultural authority that trains renewed attention on the political determinants of apartheid. The exceptionalism of the prize and of his presence on the stage draw into the light the prevarication of South African exceptionalism and direct accountability back to the hosts he addresses. On the stage in Stockholm, Soyinka assumes

the dual roles of author and mouthpiece and condemns apartheid South Africa as Europe's "monstrous child" (1987, 767). Cannily aware of the cultural capital accruing to the Nobel Prize and its implication in the very structures that he condemns in his address, Soyinka simultaneously exploits and exposes the award's Eurocentrism. The fame conferred upon him is put into dialogue with South Africa's infamy, and his own hypervisibility is made to insinuate Mandela's invisibility. The decision to address apartheid as a metonym for European and indeed for global racism signals a realignment of the parameters of literary celebrity. Directed towards the political rather than the personal, celebrity becomes a means to endorse a substantive, ethical activism designed to realize the end that Soyinka articulates in the Nobel Prize lecture: "the eradication of human inequality and the dismantling of all its structures" (1987, 771).

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the European Research Council under the European Union's Seventh Framework Programmed (FP/2007-2013) / ERC Grant Agreement no. 615564. My thanks to Professor Louise Bethlehem for her guidance and incisive remarks and to Dr. Tal Zalmanovich for her helpful comments.

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